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DAYANARA P. BESA, PhD

Faculty

Sultan Kudarat State University

dayanara.besa@umindanao.edu.ph

“SEE YOU WHEN I SEE YOU”

How are you, love, where have you been?
You linger still in thoughts unseen.
Since December, when paths entwined,
You lit a flame in this heart of mine.

Because of you, I write once more,
My silent soul begins to soar.
With every glance, with every smile,
You made my world feel so worthwhile.

I miss the way you looked my way,
The words you found, the things you'd say.
Your gentle care, your quiet grace,
The warmth I saw upon your face.

Your teeth so bright, your aura clear,
Your presence always drawing near.
Each day, you dared to speak to me—
A courage bold, yet soft and free.

You are the standard, none compare,
A light that lingers in the air.
I hope you're well, I hope you find
The joy you seek, the peace of mind.

May your dreams bloom, your spirit shine,
With love and grace in every line.
And if the stars would choose to play,
May fate bring us again someday.

Till then, I'll keep this hope in view—
See you when I see you,
John.

